

Use case catalogue v2

March 2026

What is the catalogue?

The Use Case Catalogue provides a structured overview of the use cases developed within the O-CEI and COP-PILOT Large Scale Pilots (LSPs), showcasing how Cloud-Edge-IoT (CEI) solutions are applied across different domains and market verticals.

It highlights key elements such as:

- Technology Readiness Levels (TRLs) to indicate maturity
- The Hourglass model to illustrate ecosystem interactions and interoperability
- Value chains, stakeholders, and deployment contexts
- Expected outcomes

Overall, the catalogue serves as a reference framework to understand, compare, and communicate the innovation, impact, and scalability of CEI-based solutions across pilots and use cases.

O-CEI (Open Cloud-Edge-IoT Platform Uptake in Large-Scale Cross-Domain Pilots) is an EU-funded project that is building an open Cloud-Edge-IoT platform and reusable blueprints to create a digital backbone for energy flexibility across Europe. It focuses on secure, interoperable, and reliable CEI infrastructures, using large-scale pilots to support more sustainable, efficient, and resilient digital services in sectors such as energy, mobility, agrifood, and smart cities.

COP-PILOT is an EU-funded project that is developing a Collaborative Open Platform to orchestrate end-to-end services across edge computing, 5G, and IoT environments. The project focuses on creating a secure, interoperable, standards-aligned framework that supports large-scale pilots in sectors such as energy, smart cities, agriculture, and manufacturing.

CEI-SPHERE is an EU-funded project that supports the development of an open, interoperable, and competitive Cloud-Edge-IoT (CEI) ecosystem. At its core are Europe's Large-Scale Pilots (LSPs) – the O-CEI and COP-PILOT projects – which deliver hyper-distributed, scalable next-generation CEI solutions serving a wide range of industries.

Spheres are collaborative environments that cluster use cases and pilots around key market verticals: energy and infrastructure, mobility and logistics, and industrial optimisation. They bring together stakeholders facing similar challenges to foster collaboration, reduce fragmentation, and accelerate the adoption of Cloud-Edge-IoT solutions.

Sphere 1: The Energy and infrastructure resilience sphere focuses on digital technologies, data and automation to reinforce energy systems and critical infrastructures, so they remain secure, reliable and efficient under stress or disruption.

Sphere 2: The Mobility, logistics and the software-defined vehicle (SDV) sphere addresses data-driven mobility, connected logistics and software-centric vehicles to enable safer, cleaner and more efficient transport services and supply chains.

Sphere 3: The Industrial optimisation and productivity sphere promotes advanced digital solutions that streamline industrial processes, enhance resource efficiency and increase the competitiveness of manufacturing and related sectors.

Ecosystem mapping uses the Hourglass Model to show how different stakeholders, technologies, and standards fit together in one picture. It helps turn a complex, fragmented landscape into a simple, shared view of the whole ecosystem.

Hourglass Model is a conceptual framework that illustrates how different layers of digital capabilities and corresponding stakeholder groups interact to create intelligent, interoperable, and scalable digital ecosystems.

Partner is an organisation that is officially part of the project or consortium, with a formal role and agreement.

Primary Sphere is the main market vertical that a scenario or use case or belongs to. It is where the scenario or use case most clearly fits in terms of its goals, stakeholders, and expected impact.

Secondary Sphere is an additional vertical that the same scenario or use case is also relevant to, but not its main focus. It highlights where the scenario or use case also creates value or has important implications, without changing where it is primarily assigned and managed.

Pilots and Use Cases

O - C E I

Pilot 1

Electric Grid performance optimization upon RES integration

Overview

The pilot consists of three locations: (i) Limerick (IE), serving electricity and heating to three neighbourhoods with a mix of residential and commercial buildings; (ii) Aran Islands (IE), an island community focusing on flexibility services and P2P in residential buildings; (iii) Krk Island (CR), facing significant fluctuations in connected users; and (iv) the “Concept Grid” demonstrator by EDF in the Isle of France, Paris (FR). The overarching motivation of P1 three components is to transition towards a greener, more efficient, and resilient energy system.

Expected outcomes

- A better grid demand calculation and response
- More efficient renewable energy integration
- Community engagement
- Consumer cost saving

Partners

UCC, EDF, Eko Kvarner, MDU, Powerledger, Smart MPower

Overview

Within the O-CEI project, this scenario enables prosumers and flexumers to trade energy, optimise consumption, and store excess energy using AI-driven tools, improving grid stability and increasing the use of renewable energy.

Partners: UCC, Smart MPower

Domain Energy

Location Aran Islands, Ireland

TRL 6

Spheres

Primary

Secondary

Expected outcomes

- To assess how the local renewable energy sources are optimised by increasing the share of on-site RES utilisation and reducing dependency on grid imports.
 - KPI:** Renewable energy utilisation: 35% improving over current 25% of RES.
- To evaluate the effectiveness of energy demand management and load shifting strategies in reducing peak electrical loads in participating homes from 3 neighbourhoods.
 - KPI:** Reduction in peak energy demand from approximately 500 kW: 20%.
- To quantify the reduction in electricity use enabled by energy monitoring, feedback and optimisation, demonstrating measurable efficiency gains in participating households.
 - KPI:** Reduction in energy consumption (b/a O-CEI): $\geq 20\%$ reduction based upon a baseline of 10,000 kWh/year.

Ecosystem mapping

Overview

Sensor data and smart controls dynamically manage heating for energy efficiency using edge computing.

Partners: UCC, Smart MPower

Domain Energy

Location Limerick, Ireland

TRL 6

Spheres

Primary

Secondary

Ecosystem mapping

Expected outcomes

- To quantify the reduction in electricity use enabled by energy monitoring, feedback and optimisation, demonstrating measurable efficiency gains in participating households.
 - KPI:** Reduction in energy consumption (b/a O-CEI): $\geq 20\%$ reduction based upon a baseline of 10,000 kWh/year.
- To evaluate how energy use optimisation, comfort insights and user-facing dashboards improve overall thermal comfort and satisfaction within households.
 - KPI:** User satisfaction (per surveys and formal feedback): $\geq 40\%$ improvement in comfort (typical baseline 60%).
- To quantify reductions in residential CO₂ emissions achieved through lower energy consumption and improved operational efficiency.
 - KPI:** CO₂ reduction (sensors): 30% reduction in residential spaces (baseline: 5 tons/household/year).

Overview

Seasonal demand patterns are optimised with renewable integration and decentralized learning models.

Partners: Eko Kvarner, Powerledger, Smart MPower, UCC

Domain Energy

Location Krk Island, Croatia

TRL 5

Spheres

Primary

Secondary

Expected outcomes

- To quantify improvements in renewable energy integration across mixed-generation systems (PV, biomass, grid), demonstrating better consumption–production alignment.
 - KPI:** Renewable energy utilisation: 35% improving over current 25% of RES.
- To measure the ability of demand-response tools and scheduling controls to flatten commercial and residential demand peaks, improving grid stability.
 - KPI:** Reduction in peak energy demand from approximately 500 kW: 20%.
- To demonstrate the financial impact of energy optimisation measures by reducing household energy bills through behavioural change, load shifting and improved awareness of consumption.
 - KPI:** Reduction in energy consumption (b/a O-CEI): ≥15% reduction in energy bills (baseline €1,200/year).

Ecosystem mapping

Overview

Synchronizing renewable energy for household appliances and EVs ensures comfort and charging availability.

Partners: UCC, EKO

Domain Energy

Location Krk Island, Croatia

TRL 5

Spheres

Primary

Secondary

Ecosystem mapping

Expected outcomes

- To assess improvements in user comfort and perceived energy quality resulting from enhanced monitoring, digital engagement and energy-efficiency interventions.
 - KPI:** User satisfaction (per surveys and formal feedback): $\geq 40\%$ improvement in comfort (typical baseline 60%).
- To measure the decrease in CO₂ emissions in commercial buildings enabled by optimised energy management and increased efficiency of heating, cooling and equipment loads.
 - KPI:** CO₂ reduction (sensors): $\geq 35\%$ in commercial spaces.

Overview

IoT gateways and secure O-CEI utilities empower users to monitor energy use and promote grid flexibility.

Partners: EDF

Domain Energy

Location Île-de-France, Paris, France

TRL 5

Spheres

Primary

Secondary

Expected outcomes

- Quantify the energy consumption reduction achieved by providing users with real-time data and actionable propositions.
 - KPI:** Reduction in total energy consumption over the evaluation period (%).
- Quantify the reduction in household peak power demand resulting from user engagement and load shifting recommendations.
 - KPI:** Reduction in peak power demand over the evaluation period (%).

Ecosystem mapping

Overview

Proactive scheduling for appliances like electric water heaters and space heaters, will enhance grid capacity and user comfort using edge computing and robust connectivity.

Partners: EDF

Domain Energy
Location Île-de-France, Paris, France
TRL 4

Spheres

Primary

Secondary

Expected outcomes

- Quantify the reduction in household peak power demand resulting from user engagement and load shifting recommendations.
 - KPI:** Reduction in peak power demand over the evaluation period (%).
- Quantify the performance gain of the decentralised, virtualised control architecture and its ability to improve voltage stability, thereby enabling higher RES integration.
 - KPI:** Grid voltage stability: Up to +5% of gain in voltage regulation performance (current voltage variation $\pm 5\%$).

Ecosystem mapping

Pilot 2

Software Defined Vehicle
for VaS in Urban Areas

Overview

Pilot 2 aims at upscaling the innovations performed by AUMOVIO on the project XRECO by embedding a Software Defined Vehicle circulating across Timisoara (Romania).

Expected outcomes

- Faster response to critical events by VaS software
- Reduction in emissions
- Reduction of accident rates

Partners

Aumovio, ERTICO, FENIX2.0

Overview

Enhances vehicle safety with AI-driven system monitoring, OTA updates, advanced cybersecurity, and real-time technologies for the reliable, secure, and dynamic operation of embedded systems (e.g., engine management, braking, steering, infotainment)

Partners: Aumovio, ERTICO, FENIX2.0

Domain Mobility

Location Timisoara, Romania

TRL 4

Spheres

Primary

Secondary

Expected outcomes

- To increase the transmission rate of detected vehicle incidents while driving from 87% to 99%.
 - KPI:** 20% less time reacting to incidents.

Ecosystem mapping

Overview

Leverages AI utilities from the O-CEI marketplace to optimise EV powertrain efficiency, minimize carbon footprints, and ensure driver engagement with sustainable, real-time feedback and seamless integration.

Partners: Aumovio, ERTICO, FENIX2.0

Domain Mobility

Location Timisoara, Romania

TRL 6

Spheres

Primary

Secondary

Ecosystem mapping

Expected outcomes

- To demonstrate that the average energy and fuel demand of selected test vehicles in Romania's Pilot 2, measured at 120% of the Worldwide Harmonized Light Vehicle Test Procedure (WLTP) benchmark, can be reduced by 15%.
 - KPI:** 15% reduction of non-exhaust emissions.

Overview

Uses AI to optimise EV charging and energy return via Vehicle-to-Grid (V2G) capabilities, with edge and cloud software supporting fleet-wide data analysis and operations.

Partners: Aumovio, ERTICO, FENIX2.0

Domain Mobility

Location Timisoara, Romania

TRL 5

Spheres

Primary

Secondary

Expected outcomes

- To demonstrate that Software-Defined Vehicle (VaS) capabilities can reduce electric energy consumption per vehicle kilometre by up to 15% for selected EVs.
 - KPI:** 15% reduction of energy consumption of VaS vehicles.

Ecosystem mapping

Overview

Uses V2G, smart grids, and AI to optimise energy use, schedule charging during off-peak hours, utilize dynamic pricing, and grid balancing for sustainable vehicle interactions.

Partners: Aumovio, ERTICO, FENIX2.0

Domain Mobility

Location Timisoara, Romania

TRL 5

Spheres

Primary

Secondary

Expected outcomes

- To demonstrate that Software-Defined Vehicle (VaS) capabilities can reduce electric energy consumption per vehicle kilometre by up to 15% for selected EVs.
 - KPI:** 15% reduction of energy consumption of VaS vehicles.

Ecosystem mapping

Pilot 3

Energy consumption and emission reductions in postal service fleet operation via intelligent BEV charging strategies

Overview

Charging infrastructure combined with technologies able to offer intelligent EV strategies will benefit the whole electromobility value chain. Fleet managers, energy suppliers and OEMs alike can differentiate in the market by reducing total cost of ownership - which greatly favours from energy consumption minimisation - or by prioritising the adoption of BEVs to eliminate tailpipe emissions.

Expected outcomes

- Optimisation strategy fleet operations
- Deployment of intelligent storage strategies
- Enabling a Monitoring and adaption framework
- Modelling fleet for using vehicles as mobile energy storage

Partners

Austrian Postal Service, AVL, Energie Steiermark

Overview

This use case analyses the power infrastructure (PV panels, batteries, charging infrastructure), the control and communication infrastructure, and the various communication protocols. This knowledge will then be used to optimise the location and operation of battery systems.

Partners: Austrian Postal Service, AVL, Energie Steiermark

Domain Mobility
Location Austria
TRL 6

Spheres

Primary

Secondary

Expected outcomes

- To enable the POST to choose a charging strategy to reduce the energy consumption.
 - KPI:** 15-20% Reduction (for fleet operator) of peak load.
 - KPI:** 10-15% Reduction (for fleet operator) of charging costs.
- Improve accuracy of the energy consumption prediction for the Post Depot (Mean Absolute Error < 20%).
- To enable the POST to select charging strategies that reduce fleet energy consumption and total operating cost.
 - KPI:** 5% reduction of carbon dioxide (CO2) emissions.

Ecosystem mapping

Overview

Optimises EVs as mobile storage units, utilizing O-CEI for intelligent charging, discharging, and fleet route planning, enhancing fleet resilience and battery autonomy. We will assess the economic balance of EV battery state of health degradation vs. revenue from providing energy to the grid at market price.

Partners: Austrian Postal Service, AVL, Energie Steiermark

Domain	Mobility
Location	Austria
TRL	6

Spheres

Primary

Secondary

Expected outcomes

- Using cross-domain data sharing from 5 individual sources to improve the business value chain for the post fleet (improved TCO) and the Energy Steiermark (Optimized energy procurement).
- Successfully demonstrating an agentic AI Cloud-Edge-IoT solution using cross-domain data sharing and updating every 15 minutes to constantly improve the business value chain for Post and Energie Steiermark.
- To enable the POST to choose a charging strategy to reduce the energy consumption.
 - **KPI:** 15-20% Reduction (for fleet operator) of peak load.
 - **KPI:** 10-15% Reduction (for fleet operator) of charging costs.

Ecosystem mapping

Overview

This scenario, developed within the O-CEI project, evaluates mobile energy storage systems, such as delivery vans, to support grid peak shaving and reactive power management.

Partners: Austrian Postal Service, AVL, Energie Steiermark

Domain Mobility
Location Austria
TRL 6

Spheres

Primary

Secondary

Expected outcomes

- Improve accuracy of the energy consumption prediction for the Post Depot (Mean Absolute Error < 20%).
- Successfully demonstrating an agentic AI Cloud-Edge-IoT solution using cross-domain data sharing and updating every 15 minutes to constantly improve the business value chain for Post and Energie Steiermark.
- To enable the POST to choose a charging strategy to reduce the energy consumption.
 - **KPI:** 15-20% Reduction (for fleet operator) of peak load.
 - **KPI:** 10-15% Reduction (for fleet operator) of charging costs.
- To enable the POST to select charging strategies that reduce fleet energy consumption and total operating cost.
 - **KPI:** 5% reduction of carbon dioxide (CO2) emissions.

Ecosystem mapping

Pilot 4

Variable demand in
challenging maritime
terminal landscape

Overview

Pilot four will focus on Malta and its Freeport, which has become the largest transshipment port in the Mediterranean. Maritime industry stakeholders now face multiple challenges to improve sustainability, standing out the shift from fossil fuel to electricity at terminals and vessels. Thus, the energy distribution in Malta governed by ENEMALTA will be stressed since large amounts (up to 20 MVA) will be consumed during load/unload operations of 6 simultaneous vessels, and very little when leaving.

Expected outcomes

- Energy grid digital mirror that supports forthcoming energy peaks predictions at the terminal area, by means of AI/ML-based algorithms
- Real-time energy control system that balances the connected assets based on a well-proved priority strategy

Partners

Awake.ai, CMA CGM, Enemalta, Prodevelop, Schneider Electric

Overview

The O-CEI platform will integrate energy flows from berthed vessels, using decentralized monitoring, IoT, and cybersecurity utilities to minimize blackouts and optimise energy control through orchestration and real-time dashboards.

Partners: Awake.ai, CMA CGM, Prodevelop, Schneider Electric

Domain Logistics
Location Malta
TRL 4

Spheres

Primary

Secondary

Expected outcomes

- Develop accurate AI/ML-based energy forecasting models so the terminal can anticipate demand, optimise resources, reduce power peaks and emissions, and reliably track performance over the project's intermediate and final phases.
 - KPI:** Accuracy of energy consumption predictions at MFT and its surroundings by AI/ML models: coefficient of determination (R^2) > 0.8, Median Absolute Percentage Error (MdAPE) < 20%.

Ecosystem mapping

Overview

This scenario integrates terminal asset energy data with O-CEI orchestration, coordinating peak power demands from Container Handling Equipment (CHE), and refers to avoid unnecessary peaks, with individual control systems.

Partners: Awake.ai, Enemalta, Prodevelop, Schneider Electric

Domain Logistics
Location Malta
TRL 2

Spheres

Primary

Secondary

Ecosystem mapping

Expected outcomes

- Implement a smart energy management system at MFT to optimise energy use, cut CO₂ emissions, reduce power peaks and operational costs, and enable measurable tracking of the terminal's decarbonisation progress.
 - KPI:** Reduction of power peaks in the terminal thanks to the use of the smart energy management system (10%).

Overview

This scenario replaces home electricity meters with an O-CEI orchestrated control system, managing device priorities for critical services and appliances through secure data governance and pub/sub-models of the project.

Partners: Enemalta, Prodevelop, Schneider Electric

Domain Logistics
Location Malta
TRL TBC

Spheres

Primary

Secondary

Ecosystem mapping

Expected outcomes

- Implement a smart energy management system at MFT to optimise energy use, cut CO₂ emissions, reduce power peaks and operational costs, and enable measurable tracking of the terminal's decarbonisation progress.
 - KPI:** Reduction of power peaks in the terminal thanks to the use of the smart energy management system (10%).

Pilot 5

Energetically and environmentally sustainable Halloumi cheese production

Overview

Livestock farming and the dairy industry are critical sectors for the Cypriot economy, which are increasingly challenged by rising energy costs and unstable agro-environmental conditions driven by climate change. Pilot 5 addresses these challenges through the adoption of emerging Smart IoT platforms and Cloud-Edge-IoT enablers, enabling a holistic, supply-chain-wide approach spanning livestock condition monitoring, energy aware production planning and sustainability assessment of final dairy products.

Expected outcomes

- Energy-efficient, data-driven operations, enabling dynamic optimisation and footprint-aware production.
- Autonomous edge-based monitoring and actuation, improving animal welfare and operational stability.
- Semantic, trusted data sharing across the supply chain, replacing fragmented practices.

Partners

Green Supply Chain - DIH, EMBIO Diagnostics, Charalambides Christis

Overview

Optimises energy use in livestock stables while reducing animal heat stress, using IoT sensors for environmental monitoring, livestock behaviour assessment, and HVAC control. Data is collected, harmonised and processed at the edge to support energy use forecasting and optimisation considering efficient and stable milk production and ensuring animal welfare.

Partners: Green Supply Chain, EMBIO Diagnostics, Charalambides Christis

Domain Agriculture
Location Cyprus
TRL 7

Spheres

Primary

Secondary

Ecosystem mapping

Expected outcomes

- Improve the energy efficiency of dairy production processes, reducing total energy consumption per 1,000 kg of halloumi cheese by 20%, thereby contributing to more sustainable and cost-effective operations.
 - **KPI:** 20% reduction of total energy consumption for dairy production.
- To reduce the negative effects of heat stress on dairy cattle by 20%, improving animal welfare and maintaining stable milk production during hot months.
 - **KPI:** 20% reduction of heat stress impact on cattle.
- Improve energy efficiency and resilience in in-farm milk production by enabling real-time energy-aware monitoring and response to energy consumption to reduce costs and improve environmental sustainability.
 - **KPI:** Achieve effective real-time detection and reaction for at least 80% of relevant energy-related energy events, from a baseline of no automated awareness or reaction capability.

P5 | UC2 Controlled sharing of data from various stables to the dairy production factory

Overview

O-CEI mechanisms and marketplace will securely share trusted farm data such as milk quality, feed mix, and energy footprint, using AI to forecast parameters, optimise energy consumption, and improve production practices with secure data management.

Partners: Green Supply Chain, EMBIO Diagnostics, Charalambides Christis

Domain Agriculture
Location Cyprus
TRL 7

Spheres

Primary

Secondary

Ecosystem mapping

Expected outcomes

- Improve the energy efficiency of dairy production processes, reducing total energy consumption per 1,000 kg of halloumi cheese by 20%, thereby contributing to more sustainable and cost-effective operations.
 - **KPI:** 20% reduction of total energy consumption for dairy production.
- Improve energy efficiency and resilience in in-farm milk production by enabling real-time energy-aware monitoring and response to energy consumption to reduce costs and improve environmental sustainability.
 - **KPI:** Achieve effective real-time detection and reaction for at least 80% of relevant energy-related energy events, from a baseline of no automated awareness or reaction capability.

Overview

Optimises cheese production energy sources (grid, solar) based on demand, availability, and price. The O-CEI models and Decision Support System support cost reduction, lower environmental impact and efficient operation of dairy production process.

Partners: Green Supply Chain, EMBIO Diagnostics, Charalambides Christis

Domain Agriculture
Location Cyprus
TRL 6

Spheres

Primary

Secondary

Expected outcomes

- Improve the energy efficiency of dairy production processes, reducing total energy consumption per 1,000 kg of halloumi cheese by 20%, thereby contributing to more sustainable and cost-effective operations.
 - **KPI:** 20% reduction of total energy consumption for dairy production.
- To reduce the overall environmental footprint of halloumi cheese production by 15% through improved resource efficiency, sustainable practices and lower greenhouse gas emissions across the value chain.
 - **KPI:** 15% reduction of environmental footprint of the final halloumi cheese product.

Ecosystem mapping

Overview

Aggregates energy consumption data across the farm-production chain, to calculate batch-level energy and environmental footprint. Using O-CEI orchestration and IoT-edge-cloud elements it provides trusted, traceable digital evidence to support sustainability assessment, auditing, and regulatory reporting of Halloumi cheese production.

Partners: Green Supply Chain, EMBIO Diagnostics, Charalambides Christis

Domain Agriculture
Location Cyprus
TRL 7

Spheres

Primary

Secondary

Expected outcomes

- To reduce the overall environmental footprint of halloumi cheese production by 15% through improved resource efficiency, sustainable practices and lower greenhouse gas emissions across the value chain.
 - KPI:** 15% reduction of environmental footprint of the final halloumi cheese product.
- Trusted digital evidence to support product sustainability labels and Corporate Sustainability Reporting Directive (CSRD) aligned regulatory reporting.

Ecosystem mapping

Pilot 6

Smart re-charging and efficiency of robot tractors in large fruit production fields

Overview

Greenhouse gas emissions from fruits and vegetables production primarily stem from energy use, mainly fossil fuel consumption for machinery and equipment. While specific emissions may vary, adopting electric tractors can significantly reduce greenhouse gas emissions compared to traditional diesel-powered tractors, catapulting the agriculture sector towards decarbonisation, new business models and revenue streams.

Expected outcomes

- Energy efficiency improvement of electric tractor tasks
- Environmental impact reduction of such tasks
- Reduction in operational costs
- Less downtime caused by battery-related issues

Partners

Agrimac, Garaia, Innovalia, AGRIA ZE (Zettrack)

Overview

The O-CEI platform will offer tools to be integrated in the Zetrack app and provide farmers with energy optimization suggestions, managing fleet, climate, and location data. It will propose action plans for efficient area coverage and extended charging downtime, using real-time services.

Partners: Agrimac, Garaia, Innovalia, AGRIA ZE (Zetrack)

Domain Agriculture
Location Spain
TRL 5

Spheres

Primary

Secondary

Expected outcomes

- To monitor live energy data while demonstrating how IoT based monitoring and edge analytics can reduce e-tractor energy use, enabling farmers to make more efficient decisions.
 - KPI:** Reduction of energy consumption of 50% (kWh/ha*year) compared to annual l/ha.
- To validate predictive charging and scheduling, minimising downtime and CO2 footprint.
 - KPI:** Reduction of greenhouse gas emissions (kgCO2-eq.) 0.24-0.48kg per kg of kiwi produced (over current 0.6 to 1.2 kgCO2-eq.)

Ecosystem mapping

Overview

The O-CEI AI-block will optimise agricultural tasks in kiwi plantations, using state-of-the-art models for efficient operations and route planning, with real-time data storage and semi-autonomic management.

Partners: Agrimac, Garaia, Innovalia, AGRIA ZE (Zettrack)

Domain Agriculture
Location Spain
TRL 5

Spheres

Primary

Secondary

Expected outcomes

- To optimise navigation and scheduling of tasks within the field using AI utilities from the Marketplace to cut downtime and energy waste.
 - KPI:** Time to collect, analyse and act upon (un)expected event: reduction of 70% (over current 2h).
- To monitor live energy data while demonstrating how IoT based monitoring and edge analytics can reduce e-tractor energy use, enabling farmers to make more efficient decisions.
 - KPI:** Reduction of energy consumption of 50% (kWh/ha*year) compared to annual I/ha.

Ecosystem mapping

Overview

The tractors in this pilot will optimise battery charging through edge analytics and AI predictions, either autonomously or via a farmer-controlled app, minimizing battery use, extending lifespan, and reducing costs for improved sustainability.

Partners: Agrimac, Garaia, Innovalia, AGRIA ZE (Zettrack)

Domain Agriculture

Location Spain

TRL 4

Spheres

Primary

Secondary

Ecosystem mapping

Expected outcomes

- To optimise navigation and scheduling of tasks within the field using AI utilities from the Marketplace to cut downtime and energy waste.
 - KPI:** Time to collect, analyse and act upon (un)expected event: reduction of 70% (over current 2h).
- To validate predictive charging and scheduling, minimising downtime and CO2 footprint.
 - KPI:** Reduction of greenhouse gas emissions (kgCO2-eq.) 0.24-0.48kg per kg of kiwi produced (over current 0.6 to 1.2 kgCO2-eq.)

Pilot 7

Trustworthy and secure EV
charging upon reliable 5G
networks

Overview

The potential that 5G holds in making EV charging more efficient is clear. With lower latency and highly reliable communications, EV chargers can share real time EV data, opening up for innovative (AI-based) developments in flexible grid management and optimisation on IoT and distributed control techniques. Also, new business models can appear (e.g., apps for smart reservation, rewarding optimal grid and moment selection...).

Expected outcomes

- Cost saving in EV charging
- Better efficiency in regular and critical (reactive power needs) situations
- Grid stability and security improvement
- Guidelines for EV swarm learning based pattern recognition

Partners

Ares2T, CERTH, E-GAP, Nova

Overview

Transforms chargers into “intelligent” bidirectional elements, optimising grid power flow through O-CEI microservices data management, and 5G’s low-latency, ensuring efficient load balancing and reduced environmental impact.

Partners: Ares2T, CERTH, E-GAP, Nova

Domain Telecom
Location Italy
TRL 5

Spheres

Primary

Secondary

Expected outcomes

- Measuring the cost saving enabled by smart charging from the Charging Point Operator’s perspective with respect to the single smart charging session impacting on the final cost for the customer.
 - KPI:** >5% of cost savings for the end user w.r.t. to the Italian market (average costs for a fast charge in DC in the range €1-€0.90 per kWh).
- Measuring the peak shaving capacity of the load area management system to improve grid stability.
 - KPI:** <0,1% daily peaks in power consumption.
- Measuring the effectiveness of the load area management system in the smart charging remote control.
 - KPI:** <0,01s reaction time to smart charging requests.

Ecosystem mapping

Overview

This use case, aligned with the O-CEI blueprint, incorporates security measures, data sovereignty, and auditing to ensure trustworthy data flows from sensors and EVs, supporting energy balancing decisions with continuous monitoring and response to cyber threats.

Partners: Ares2T, CERTH, E-GAP, Nova.

Domain Telecom
Location Italy
TRL 6

Spheres

Primary

Secondary

Expected outcomes

- Measuring the efficiency of the load area management system to improve monitoring services.
 - **KPI:** >99% up time of smart charging monitor service.
- Measuring the effectiveness of the load area management system in the smart charging remote control.
 - **KPI:** <0,01s reaction time to smart charging requests.

Ecosystem mapping

Pilot 8

Heightened social
engagement and
acceptability of energy
flexibility in urban areas

Overview

The goal is to foster prosumers into the increasingly liberalised energy market pursuing high social acceptability, enabling them to reap new forms of electricity production and consumption. The pilot is deployed at three locations in Switzerland, that engage users and energy flexibility in four types of buildings: (i) urban apartments (Meyrin and Fribourg), (ii) single family homes (Fribourg), (iii) administrative buildings (Fribourg) and, (iv) ski villages (Valais).

Expected outcomes

- To deploy flexibility applications and having them exposed for end users benefit
- A better control of electricity demand/production through LLM
- To properly model social prosumer engagement profiling

Partners

CLEMAP, HES-SO, Polygones, Val D'Anniviers, Groupe E

Overview

Deals with flexibility applications that enable DSOs to ensure Grid stability and LECs to optimise their consumption costs and minimise their dependence on DSOs.

Partners: CLEMAP, HES-SO, Polygones, Groupe E

Domain Urban

Location Meyrin, Switzerland

TRL 5

Spheres

Primary

Secondary

Expected outcomes

- To assess and model the social acceptance of prosumers toward energy flexibility and smart services, enabling better design of engagement strategies and policy recommendations.
 - KPI:** 500 prosumers social acceptance profiles.
- To improve control of electricity demand and production through LLMs, with Smart Readiness Indicator (SRI) levels measured before and after the deployment of the solutions.
 - KPI:** Increase the energy flexibility efficiency by 12%, measured using the Smart Readiness Indicator (SRI) to rate building smart readiness before and after deployment and measure fluctuation.

Ecosystem mapping

Overview

This use case focuses on charging stations for electric vehicles (EVs). It enables EV owners to optimise vehicle charging through smart contracts, and new business models

Partners: CLEMAP, HES-SO, Val D'Anniviers, Groupe E

Domain Urban

Location Meyrin, Switzerland

TRL 5

Spheres

Primary

Secondary

Expected outcomes

- To foster the development and deployment of Smart Energy Services (SES) in urban, administrative, and tourism buildings, with pilot machine-learning outputs exposed to end users through SES.

Ecosystem mapping

Overview

This use case is related to touristic resorts. It enables hotels, restaurants and ski resorts to optimise their energy consumption. The goal is to improve efficiency in villages and ski stations through decentralised analytics and continuous updates.

Partners: CLEMAP, HES-SO, Val D'Anniviers

Domain Urban

Location Meyrin, Switzerland

TRL 5

Spheres

Primary

Secondary

Ecosystem mapping

Expected outcomes

- To foster the development and deployment of Smart Energy Services (SES) in urban, administrative, and tourism buildings, with pilot machine-learning outputs exposed to end users through SES.
- To improve control of electricity demand and production through LLMs, with Smart Readiness Indicator (SRI) levels measured before and after the deployment of the solutions.
 - KPI:** Increase the energy flexibility efficiency by 12%, measured using the Smart Readiness Indicator (SRI) to rate building smart readiness before and after deployment and measure fluctuation.

Clusters and Use Cases

coppilot

Cluster 1

Business Integration in Mining

Overview

This cluster consists of a series of use cases deployed in Norrbotten, Kiruna, and Luleå, where each partner already has individual products operational with the customer. The cluster integrates information and computing platforms to unify data and analytics from three core areas: (i) real-time monitoring of logistic infrastructure (ii) rock seismic data collection and analytics and (iii) production machinery data collection and predictive maintenance.

Expected outcomes

- Collaborative Edge-to-Cloud continuum for mining, with dynamic provisioning and autoscaling across IoT, edge and cloud.
- Edge-local preprocessing that cuts transmitted data by up to 60%, lowering bandwidth needs and latency.
- Cross-company interoperability with 4+ partners using standardized APIs (e.g. Arrowhead, FIWARE).
- Improved safety and uptime via early seismic warnings and remote predictive maintenance.

Partners

Luleå University of Technology, RISE Research Institutes of Sweden, Rocksigma AB, ThingWave, Predge, Hosch, LTU Business

Overview

This use case focuses on large-scale micro-seismic sensing, data collection, and processing for underground mining. Significant financial incentives drive this effort, as demonstrated by a large seismic event that forced part of a mine to be closed, leaving ore worth billions of euros inaccessible.

Domain Industry

Location Norrbotten, Sweden

TRL 6

Spheres

Primary

Secondary

Expected outcomes

- Scalable and distributed compute solution.
- Multi-vendor and multi-technology sensor support.
- Substantial increase in analysis capacity (number of sensors).

Ecosystem mapping

Overview

This use case addresses the monitoring challenges of critical infrastructure and logistics. Key success factors include live asset tracking, accurate infrastructure data and decision support software.

Domain Industry
Location Norrbotten, Sweden
TRL 6

Spheres

Primary

Secondary

Expected outcomes

- Large scale deployments of rock bolts for positioning assets and staff.
- Reduced deployment time through automated rock bolt installation and configuration, substantial increase in sensor support.
- Collaborative sensing solution and data sharing with partners for advanced data processing.

Ecosystem mapping

Overview

Ensuring uninterrupted material flow and logistics is vital for mining operations, particularly where limited or no stockpiles exist to buffer against unplanned downtimes within the logistics chain.

Domain Industry

Location Norrbotten, Sweden

TRL 6

Spheres

Primary

Secondary

Expected outcomes

- Reduced onboarding time.
- Increase the degree of automation to onboard data sources and users for decision support.

Ecosystem mapping

Overview

The future of digital services in underground mining is evolving into a complex ecosystem of distributed hardware, low-power IoT devices, edge computing nodes (for minimal latency), and mission-critical data centres. This use case will act as the integration platform for UC#1.1 through UC#1.3, uniting their data and analytics streams for customers.

Domain Industry
Location Norrbotten, Sweden
TRL 6

Spheres

Primary **Secondary**

Expected outcomes

- Edge-to-cloud continuum framework solution.
- Increased resource utilization of distributed hardware through automated system orchestration.
- Deployment of and management of distributed compute infrastructures.

Ecosystem mapping

Cluster 2

Smart Sustainable IoT
Solutions in Valencia

Overview

As the European Green Capital 2024, Valencia is piloting smart sustainable IoT solutions across several real-life environments. The cluster includes the city of Valencia, the Port of Valencia, the industrial park of Almussafes, and the Universitat Politècnica de València (UPV) campus, a controlled smart city environment working towards carbon neutrality by 2030. By deploying cloud-based smart IoT platforms with distributed intelligence, this cluster aims to collect and analyse data to drive AI-powered decisions for urban sustainability, energy optimization, and environmental quality.

Expected outcomes

- Smoother traffic flow, better public transport services, improved urban planning via real-time vehicle data.
- Quicker flood alerts and better evacuation strategies to reduce harm to people and infrastructure.
- Lower emissions, smarter waste handling, reduced carbon footprint, data-driven environmental decisions.
- Safer port operations, fewer accidents, more efficient docking, reduced logistics costs.

Partners

Universidad Politècnica de Valencia, Fundación Valenciaport, Valencia Innovation Capital, Ajuntament d'Almussafes, Telefónica, Nespra, Fivecomm

Overview

Real-time monitoring of key urban areas in Valencia and the Almussafes Industrial Park will be achieved using sensors, radars, cameras, and other IoT devices. These data streams will facilitate AI-driven decision-making for improving sustainable mobility and environmental management. The Smart IoT Platform of Valencia will provide access to this data, with some of it exposed to third-party developers via open calls.

Domain Industry

Location Valencia, Spain

TRL 7

Spheres

Primary

Secondary

Expected outcomes

- **Reduced Traffic Congestion:** Improved traffic flow through data-driven optimizations.
- **Enhanced Road Safety:** Real-time alerts and insights help reduce accident rates.
- **Informed Urban Planning:** Data-backed decisions for better transportation policies.
- **Environmental Benefits:** Reduction in emissions due to optimized traffic movements.
- **Improved Public Transport Efficiency:** Dynamic route adjustments based on real-time demand.
- **Improved Safety by early detection and real time monitorization of flood event:** Real-time information on flood event evolution.

Ecosystem mapping

Overview

At the UPV campus, IoT devices will monitor energy consumption, water usage, waste management, and environmental conditions, among other parameters, in real time. This data will be integrated into a smart IoT platform for analysis to identify patterns, trends, and opportunities for optimization. The goal is to support the campus in achieving net-zero carbon neutrality while testing sustainability-focused tools and mechanisms.

Domain Industry

Location Valencia, Spain

TRL 7

Spheres

Primary

Secondary

Expected outcomes

- Obtain accurate data on waste generation by type and container.
- Reduce environmental impact through collection optimization.
- Implement tools to improve collection routes.
- Enhance traceability and sustainability of the carbon footprint.

Ecosystem mapping

Overview

The Port of Valencia will serve as a testbed for managing maritime and terrestrial traffic. A smart IoT platform will be deployed to support precise maritime tracking, real-time risk assessment during berthing, and enhanced monitoring of truck movements. These advancements will aim to improve safety, operational efficiency, and sustainability.

Domain Industry

Location Valencia, Spain

TRL 7

Spheres

Primary

Secondary

Expected outcomes

- Greater accuracy in detecting and tracking vessels in real-time.
- Reduced risk of accidents and damage to port infrastructure.
- Optimization of docking, loading, unloading, and departure times.
- Improved operational planning and more efficient resource allocation.
- Reduced operational costs due to better port traffic management.

Ecosystem mapping

Cluster 3A

AgriTech Transformation
and Sustainability
Initiative (ATSI)

Cluster 3A | AgriTech Transformation and Sustainability Initiative (ATSI)

Overview

The AgriTech Transformation and Sustainability Initiative (ATSI) is a collaborative project transforming agriculture through technologies like IoT, robotics, edge computing, and secure data management. Focused on precision farming, sustainable leafy vegetable production, and supply chain optimization, ATSI tackles challenges across the agricultural value chain to boost market competitiveness and economic growth. Key innovations include real-time crop monitoring, pest management, and Just-In-Time (JIT) logistics using IoT networks, drones, agricultural robots, and blockchain, supported by a multi-cloud platform and data lake for integrated analytics.

Expected outcomes

- Higher yields and more efficient resource use through real-time crop monitoring, targeted pest control, and precision farming.
- Lower chemical inputs, food waste, and CO₂ emissions via targeted spraying and smart JIT logistics.
- End-to-end traceability and data integrity across cultivation, harvest, and logistics using blockchain and secure data management.

Partners

AggroApps, Barba Stathis, Agricultural University of Athens, Tor Vergata University of Rome, iLink, OTE Group of Companies

Overview

This use case utilizes IoT sensors, including plant wearables, for real-time monitoring of environmental conditions and crop health. UAVs and satellite imagery deliver accurate crop health assessments and detect pest infestations, enabling precise and timely interventions.

Domain Agriculture
Location Central Macedonia; Greece
TRL 7

Spheres

Primary **Secondary**

Expected outcomes

- Real-time environmental and crop health intelligence achieved through IoT sensors, plant wearables for continuous antinutrient monitoring, UAV surveillance and satellite imagery, enabling precise crop assessments, early pest detection and targeted, data-driven interventions.

Ecosystem mapping

Overview

Autonomous UGVs with AI-powered edge processing are used for precision spraying and pest control. These Agrirobots leverage data from sensors and UAVs to execute sustainable interventions, minimizing chemical usage and improving farming efficiency.

Domain Agriculture
Location Central Macedonia; Greece
TRL 7

Spheres

Primary **Secondary**

Expected outcomes

- Autonomous, AI-driven field operations achieved through UGVs performing edge-based precision spraying and pest management, leveraging fused sensor and UAV data to deliver timely interventions, reduced chemical dependency and enhanced production sustainability.

Ecosystem mapping

Overview

A secure data framework utilizing encryption and blockchain technology safeguards data integrity and security throughout the agricultural value chain. A unified IoT network and multi-cloud orchestration platform enable seamless communication, interoperability, and data sharing across systems.

Domain Agriculture
Location Central Macedonia; Greece
TRL 5

Spheres

Primary **Secondary**

Expected outcomes

- **KPI:** Ensure end-to-end ledger transaction performance from API request to commit confirmation, measured by Ledger Transaction Commit Latency (< 10 seconds).
- **KPI:** Enable efficient internal smart contract execution at peer-node level, measured by Smart Contract Execution Time (< 500 ms).
- **KPI:** Achieve rapid automated deployment of operational peer nodes, measured by Node Deployment Time (< 10 minutes).
- **KPI:** Provide timely end-to-end verification for consumer mobile applications, measured by Time-to-Verification (< 30 seconds).
- **KPI:** Ensure high reliability of distributed ledger commits, measured by Transaction Success Rate (> 99.5%).
- **KPI:** Support sustained transactional scalability of the ledger, measured by Transaction Throughput (> 10 TPS sustained).

Ecosystem mapping

Overview

Smart JIT logistics leverage AI algorithms and real-time IoT data for route optimization and advanced tracking. This allows dynamic adjustments to operations, ensuring efficient delivery of agricultural products, minimizing waste, and reducing environmental impact.

Domain Agriculture
Location Central Macedonia; Greece
TRL 5

Spheres

Primary

Secondary

Expected outcomes

- **KPI:** Optimize the harvest-to-factory pipeline through Just-in-Time logistics, achieving a +5% improvement in ETA from harvest to factory (total unit).
- **KPI:** Reduce transport-related CO₂ emissions by 10% through optimized routing and logistics.
- **KPI:** Reduce fuel consumption across transport routes by 10% through route optimization.
- **KPI:** Optimize truck utilization and loading flow, minimizing idle and waiting time and achieving a +10% improvement in truck utilisation and waiting-time performance.
- **KPI:** Enable temperature monitoring during transport and handling, resulting in a 5% improvement in product quality preservation and reduced crop loss.

Ecosystem mapping

Cluster 3E

Edge Intelligence for
Enhancing Grid Reliability
in RES-Rich Distribution
Grids

Cluster 3E | Edge Intelligence for Enhancing Grid Reliability in RES-Rich Distribution Grids

Overview

The growing demand for low-carbon electricity is transforming power networks from passive, centralized systems into active, decentralized grids with bidirectional power flows. This cluster enhances reliability in RES-rich distribution grids in the Preveza area by combining biogas and PV units, an Aggregator (DEI), an Energy Producer (BPO), and IoT-enabled analytics for demand response and stable grid operation.

Expected outcomes

- Real-time DER control with reduced grid congestion and faster response times (<700 ms).
- Higher reliability of EV charging through predictive maintenance, reduced downtime, and >90% forecast accuracy.
- More reliable biogas generation with >99.5% uptime, accurate energy forecasts, and reduced waste products.

Partners

University of Patras, Power Public Corporation, p-NET, Enakronic PC, BIOGAS PREVEZA ONE PC

C3E | UC1 Harvesting in Real-Time Flexibility from Active Electricity Distribution Grids

Overview

This use case involves developing a cloud-edge platform for real-time flexibility harvesting. The platform will provide two primary services: Real-time Estimation of Flexibility and Optimal Control for Flexibility Provision.

Domain Energy
Location Preveza, Patras, Greece
TRL 5

Spheres

Primary **Secondary**

Expected outcomes

- Develop a unified cloud-edge real-time monitoring and control platform for active distribution grids, enabling flexibility harvesting.
- Distribution grid simulation platform with support of different DER controller simulators and communication protocols.
- Easy extension to other types of DERs.

Ecosystem mapping

Overview

As EV adoption increases, fast-charging stations become essential for meeting mobility demands. This use case promotes charger reliability by leveraging predictive maintenance and resource optimization to prevent unexpected breakdowns. The integration of two services – Hours-Ahead and Day-Ahead Forecasting and Edge Intelligence for Predictive Maintenance for preventing unexpected breakdowns and maximizing charger uptime – aims to improve user experiences.

Domain Energy

Location Patras, Greece

TRL 6

Spheres

Primary

Secondary

Expected outcomes

EV Charging station management platform ensuring:

- Uninterrupted power supply by enabling predictive maintenance in EV chargers.
- Optimal charger operation and grid stability by predicting energy demand in real-time.
- Effortless addition of new charging stations to manage.

Ecosystem mapping

C3E | UC3 Predictive Maintenance and Monitoring of Anaerobic Digestion in a Biogas Plant

Overview

To enhance the reliability of electricity grids, the efficient operation of anaerobic digestion processes in biogas plants is critical. This use case implements a predictive maintenance and monitoring system featuring: *Digital Twin Model, Predictive Maintenance, Real-time Process.*

Domain Energy
Location Preveza, Patras, Greece
TRL 6

Spheres

Primary **Secondary**

Expected outcomes

Biogas Plant & RES management platform enabling:

- Predictive maintenance.
- Power production prediction.
- Flexibility estimation.
- Effortless extension with new sensors and/or RES.

Ecosystem mapping

Cluster 4

Smart Vineyards &
Sustainable Winery
Ecosystems

Cluster 4 | Smart Vineyards & Sustainable Winery Ecosystems

Overview

This cluster harnesses IoT, ML, and AI within the federated computing continuum to manage diverse data across domains, enhancing efficiency, sustainability, and digital innovation with a strong ESG focus. It combines advanced data management and governance, including Network-as-Code and GAIA-X principles for sovereign data centres, and will roll out use cases in smart vineyards and sustainable winery ecosystems to drive a sustainable, digitally advanced transformation.

Expected outcomes

- Higher recovery and longer lifetime of reusable IoT sensors.
- Operational savings and efficiency via automation and predictive maintenance.
- Sustainability gains through lower waste and optimized water and resource use.
- Scalable AI-driven IoT platforms for accurate irrigation and real-time bottling monitoring.

Partners

OneSource, RedZinc, JIG, Terraview

Overview

This use case focuses on logistics, maintenance, and recycling of reusable IoT sensors within the wine value chain, promoting sustainability and operational efficiency.

Domain Agriculture
Location Ireland
TRL 3

Spheres

Primary **Secondary**

Expected outcomes

- Reduced sensor downtime through predictive maintenance.
 - **KPI:** ≥95% lifecycle transparency accuracy; ≥20% increase in device lifespan.
 - **KPI:** ≥30% reduction in total IoT costs.
- Improved logistics planning for replacement and recovery.
 - **KPI:** ≥80% sensor reuse rate
 - **KPI:** ≥50% reduction of IoT e-waste; ≥15% decrease in defective products
- Automated lifecycle workflows replacing manual processes.
 - **KPI:** 100% compliance audits passed
 - **KPI:** ≥80% positive user feedback

Ecosystem mapping

Overview

This use case utilizes satellite optical remote sensing and data analytics to enhance Water Use Efficiency (WUE) in agriculture. Through the implementation of precise irrigation methods, it supports ESG principles and the SDGs, fostering sustainable water management and reducing consumption.

Domain Agriculture
Location Spain
TRL 4-6

Spheres

Primary **Secondary**

Expected outcomes

- Decrease (optimize) irrigation costs and improve agricultural yields.
 - KPI:** $\geq 20\%$ reduction of water consumption.
 - KPI:** $\geq 20\%$ reduction of water consumption while keeping same crop performance.
 - KPI:** Increase of profitability $\geq 10\%$.

Ecosystem mapping

Overview

This use case utilizes a FIWARE-based IoT tool to improve winery efficiency by monitoring Overall Equipment Efficiency (OEE). It evolves into an AI/ML-powered Manufacturing Execution System (MES), enabling predictive maintenance and optimizing operations within the project's cloud infrastructure.

Domain Agriculture
Location Spain
TRL 7

Spheres

Primary

Secondary

Expected outcomes

- Real-time monitoring of the bottling line and rapid anomaly detection.
 - **KPI:** System latency - 30% reduction in downtime detection time (Labeler, Capsule Machine, etc.).
 - **KPI:** Fault resolution time - 15 minutes from detection to corrective alert.
 - **KPI:** OEE data capture accuracy - 98% accuracy
- Improved efficiency and reduced downtime, with more proactive, data-driven maintenance.
 - **KPI:** Total machine downtime reduction.
 - **KPI:** Predictive maintenance accuracy – 85% reliability in fault detection
 - **KPI:** Production cycle efficiency – Maintain pre-production times
- IoT–ERP–MES integration for unified production visibility and data-driven decision-making.
 - **KPI:** Data integration success rate - 99% ERP-MES order synchronization.
 - **KPI:** Manual data entry reduction – 40%.
- Reduction of waste (bottles, cases, materials) and better energy use, aligned with sustainability and ESG goals.
 - **KPI:** Downtime cost reduction.
 - **KPI:** Decision-making agility – 20% reduction in production adjustment time

Ecosystem mapping

C4 | UC4 AI-Driven Green Energy Vineyard Management

Overview

The use of 5G or WIFI (provided by the 5G modems deployed) IoT sensors or cameras can be deployed in some vineyards for Agricultural experiments. In collaboration with two local vineyards and wineries, the Matanza private 5G rural site, powered by solar panels and a wind generator, collects energy KPIs from the 5G network and connected devices, supports a camera-equipped quadruped robot with near-edge AI processing, and recharges agricultural AGVs and robots using on-site green energy when available.

Domain Agriculture
Location Spain
TRL 4-6

Spheres

Primary

Secondary

Expected outcomes

- Always-on connectivity in remote/off-grid areas ensuring uninterrupted telecom service.
- Priority-based power allocation ensuring critical 5G/6G infrastructure remains operational.
- Reduced operational costs minimizing fuel use, maintenance, and backup dependency.
- Predictive energy optimization aligning renewable supply with demand using weather and AI.

Ecosystem mapping

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